

Challenges Cybersecurity Architects Are Facing In A Cloud Computing Environment

Anton Allen
Texas A&M University
400 Bizzell St, College Station, USA
lilant2012@tamu.edu

Ethan Puchaty
Lockheed Martin
1 Lockheed Blvd, Fort Worth, USA

Behbood Zoghi
Texas A&M University
400 Bizzell St, College Station, USA
zoghi@tamu.edu

Abstract- In the past decade, cloud computing has become an integral part of many companies' business strategies and IT architecture. Companies look to seek and adopt new business models, increase efficiency in handling massive amount of data, handle fluctuations in computing workloads for customers and stakeholders, and gain a competitive advantage in their industry. All these concepts have to be considered while also trying to deliver a product or service, and not disrupt existing operations for the company. This paper will address the multilevel challenges and threats in cloud computing and their potential solutions.

Cloud adoption has introduced the three types of cloud computing service models. The first is the Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) model, which is defined as an instant computing infrastructure that is provisioned and managed over the internet. The second is the Platform as a Service (PaaS) model, in which companies essentially rent everything they need to build an application and rely on the cloud provider for development tools, infrastructure, and operating systems. The third is Software as a Service (SaaS) model, which is a software distribution model in which a cloud service provider will host applications for customers and makes them available over the internet.

Many companies have developed a new approach called hybrid cloud computing. The growth of the hybrid cloud model has allowed companies to use a mix of the three models with public and private clouds to create the best environment for their company's infrastructure. The top benefits of this approach include: Better security, Operating cost, improvements, and Speed and agility increase.

A hybrid cloud model can eliminate or greatly reduce trade-offs and offer the best solutions for the company. Implementation and management can still be challenging for a hybrid cloud model. Having different management tools for a private or public cloud, introduces a fragmented IT infrastructure that strongly lacks interoperability and visibly for the company.

Keywords-component; cybersecurity; cloud computing; hybrid cloud

I. BACKGROUND

Cloud computing is a new name for an old concept that has been around for years and it is simply defined as the delivery of services or resources through the internet. These resources include tools and applications like data storage, servers, databases, networking, and software. It allows businesses to have the flexibility and efficiency to meet new and growing demands in any industry. Cloud computing provides the infrastructure, software, and platforms necessary for success in today's business landscape no matter where it is needed. As the presence of cloud computing becomes more widespread, the demand for professionals who can manage and configure these cloud networks properly is also becoming more inescapable.

Since 2009, companies have been shifting their data storage and computing needs to cloud-based services and away from agency-owned or in-house data centers. This shift was led by two primary goals: reduce the total investment into Information Technology (IT), which stands at about \$90 billion each year, and take advantage of what cloud adoption offers [1]. Which is efficiency, accessibility, collaboration, rapidity of innovation, reliability, and security. However,

this adoption also led to many challenges with shifting to cloud services. IT managers expressed concerns about security in certain cloud environments, the complexity of migrating existing legacy applications to the cloud, and the lack of skilled staff to manage the cloud environments. On the government side, planning for cloud adoption began with the 2010 publication “A 25-Point Implementation Plan to Reform Federal IT Management”. Then in 2017 the “Report to President on Federal IT Modernization”, the Office of Management and Budget (OMB) pledged to update the government’s legacy Federal Cloud Computing Strategy called “Cloud First”. This effort also led to the creation of The Federal Risk and Authorization Management Program (FedRAMP) which is a government-wide program that provides a standardized approach to security assessment, authorization, and continuous monitoring for cloud products and services [1].

As cloud adoption has become standard in most industries, cybersecurity architects have to configure and manage their companies cloud infrastructures while also mitigating the challenges that come with cloud environments. This research paper will discuss many topics but will focus on three main challenges: control, security and trade-offs, and risk. With these three focus areas, the scope of the project will discuss the challenge, mitigation, and the potential solutions for these challenges.

A. *Control*

In a cloud computing environment, the level of control a company has is based on the type of service and cloud deployment model you choose. With a public cloud, all hardware, software, and other supporting infrastructure is owned and managed by the cloud provider. Employees access these services and manage their accounts using a web browser. Although, public clouds can save companies from the expensive costs of having to purchase, manage, and maintain in-house hardware and application infrastructures. The cloud service provider is held responsible for all management and maintenance of the system. This severely reduces the control for a cybersecurity architect, since they have to rely on the cloud service providers for almost all aspects of the cloud infrastructure.

A private cloud provides the cloud computing resources to be used exclusively by a single business or organization. It can be physically located on-site at a company datacenter but most companies want to rely on a cloud service provider to host their private cloud, since the services and infrastructure are maintained on a private network. Private clouds deliver a higher level of security and privacy through both company firewalls and internal hosting, to ensure operations and sensitive data are not accessible to outside parties. This elevated level of control also has one key drawback that the company’s IT department is held responsible for the cost and accountability of managing the private cloud. This leads to private clouds requiring the same staffing, management, and maintenance expenses similar to traditional ownership of a data center. This also provides a company with high assurance since the private cloud is managed by their own in-house IT department.

Most cybersecurity architects will lean more towards a hybrid cloud which combines a public and private cloud, by allowing data and applications to be shared between them. When computing and processing demand fluctuates, hybrid cloud computing gives businesses the ability to seamlessly scale their on-site infrastructure up to the public cloud to handle any overflow, without giving third-party datacenters access to all of their data. Cybersecurity architects gain the flexibility and computing power of the public cloud for basic and non-sensitive computing tasks. While keeping business-critical applications and data on-site safely behind a company firewall. Companies will pay only for resources

they temporarily use instead of having to purchase, program, and maintain additional resources and equipment that could remain idle over long periods of time. The challenge with a hybrid cloud is with multiple infrastructure platforms come increased possibilities of incompatibility of tools and processes. Also, the combination of both clouds allows data to be moved across platforms and adds an increased risk of data exposure to the company. Companies will have to determine if existing tools will suffice or if teams need to acquire and learn new tools to ensure compatibility and security.

B. Security and Tradeoffs

Security and tradeoffs can be discussed together based on the cloud service the company chooses to use for their cloud implementation. Most cloud computing services fall into three broad categories: Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Software as a Service (SaaS). These are sometimes called the cloud computing "stack" because they build on top of one another. The most basic category of cloud computing services is Infrastructure as a service (IaaS). With IaaS the cloud service provider manages the infrastructure while the company purchases, installs, configures, and manages its software, operating systems, middleware, and applications. Platform as a service (PaaS) refers to cloud computing services that supply an on-demand environment for developing, testing, delivering, and managing software applications. PaaS is designed to make it easier for developers to quickly create web or mobile apps, without worrying about setting up or managing the underlying infrastructure of servers, storage, network, and databases needed for development. The company manages the applications and services they develop, and the cloud service provider typically manages everything else. Software as a service (SaaS) is a method for delivering software applications over the internet on-demand and typically on a subscription basis. With SaaS, cloud providers host and manage the software application and underlying infrastructure and handle any maintenance, like software upgrades and security patching. All of the underlying infrastructure, middleware, app software, and app data are located in the cloud service provider's data center. Authorized users connect to the application over the internet, usually with web a browser on their phone, tablet, or PC [2].

Each service model has its tradeoffs but when it comes to security, they all face similar security challenges. An Application Program Interface (API) is the key to successful cloud integration and interoperability, it allows the end-user to interact with a cloud provider's service. Many cloud providers have their own proprietary APIs unfortunately, not every API is entirely secure. Most cloud provider's APIs are initially developed in-house and external security assessments are not conducted and are later found to be insecure. This problem is compounded when the client company has built its application layer on top of these APIs. The security vulnerability will then exist in the customer's application. This could be an internal application, or even a public-facing application potentially exposing private data. Security with cloud data has an additional set of unique challenges since data is stored with the cloud service provider and accessed over the internet. This means visibility and control over that data are limited and also raises the question of how it can be properly secured. Cloud service providers treat cloud security as a shared responsibility model in which, the cloud service provider covers the security of the cloud itself and the customer covers the security of what they put in it [2].

Figure 1, provides a depiction of the shared responsibility model for cloud security:

Shared Responsibility Model for Security in the Cloud			
On-Premises (for reference)	IaaS (Infrastructure-as-a-service)	PaaS (Platform-as-a-service)	SaaS (Software-as-a-service)
User Access	User Access	User Access	User Access
Data	Data	Data	Data
Applications	Applications	Applications	Applications
Operating System	Operating System	Operating System	Operating System
Network Traffic	Network Traffic	Network Traffic	Network Traffic
Hypervisor	Hypervisor	Hypervisor	Hypervisor
Infrastructure	Infrastructure	Infrastructure	Infrastructure
Physical	Physical	Physical	Physical

Customer Responsibility
 Cloud Provider Responsibility

Figure 1: Shared responsibility model for security in the Cloud.

C. Risks

Something that is not widely discussed in the cloud computing environment is what risks are associated with cloud computing. Risk can be broken out into five key areas: data regulatory and security, technology, operational, vendor, and financial risks. Data security and regulatory risk can be associated with loss, leakage, or unavailability of data. This can cause business interruption, loss of revenue, loss of reputation, or regulatory non-compliance. The regulatory risk is associated with non-compliance with various national/geographic regulations, industry, or service-specific legal and regulatory requirements. The technology risk can be associated with constantly evolving technologies and lack of standardization in how they integrate or interoperate. These risks could lead to costly re-architecture efforts for adoption or integration with new technologies. Operational risk can be associated with the execution of IT services and tasks that the business relies upon. Cloud migration has also brought to the forefront a new approach called DevOps, where development and operations responsibilities are merging. This allows deployment times to be cut down to days rather than weeks or months. It can have an impact on day-to-day IT operations and development teams will need to be trained in cloud deployment and management. Vendor risk comes from leverage or association with vendors. Unforeseen vendor circumstances such as bankruptcy, lawsuits, SEC probe, or any other act of defamation for the vendor could significantly damage an organization’s reputation and goodwill. This risk would apply to private and public cloud computing scenarios due to the association with and reliance on a service provider. Lastly, financial risk can be associated with overspending and loss of revenue. Companies usually underestimate the initial cost to build and maintain a cloud environment and continue to carry the capital expenditure related to hardware and software. The financial risk is mainly related to the variable nature of costs, tied to running up the cost of using the cloud due

to poor planning and requirements from the business. Managing cloud costs needs a level of focus, skill, and tools that were not required in the past [3].

D. Scope

The scope of this project will provide a deliverable on mitigation, best practices, and potential solutions to the three main challenges described earlier in this report which is: control, security and trade-offs, and risk. This deliverable will also describe how cybersecurity architects can leverage FedRAMP and DISA requirements onto the potential cloud services providers to ensure regulatory compliance is adhered to. For the security aspect, the deliverable will address actions to take before adding a cloud service to the company workflows and enforcing an external cloud security risk assessment. This risk assessment involves identifying what the biggest risks are, what their impacts would be, and how the likelihood of each risk to occur.

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodology design utilized a mixed method which is the nature of both quantitative and qualitative research. The qualitative research was based on fundamental four questions that the cyber expert was interviewed on:

1. What are the benefits of implementing Cloud Computing in your specific field/department?
2. What are the issues affecting the adoption of Cloud Computing by cyber architects?
3. How can these factors best be addressed to increase the rate of uptake and use of cloud computing?
4. What measures or procedures need to be in place to ensure the success of adoption and utilization of cloud computing?

In cloud computing quantitative research, it focused on how a company is assessing responses to a measure. One of the key benefits discussed that can be conducted is a cloud security assessment. The assessment provides an extensive report that includes the following:

- Identify cloud security risks
- A cloud security audit to document current controls and provide visibility into the strengths and weaknesses of the current systems
- Assess gaps in current capabilities that may weaken cloud security and recommend technology and services to address them
- Assess the security maturity by benchmarking current controls and practices against leading methods and standards
- Assess the effectiveness of current policies and their alignment with the company's business goals

A. Participants

As mentioned above on the four fundamental questions asked to participants that are currently in the cloud computing industry or have extensive experience in the field. The targeted number of participants were cybersecurity architects that have 5-10 years of experience in cloud computing infrastructure.

B. Instruments

In regards to instruments used; this is a very critical part of the methodology section. For this report, the instruments that were used are the four interview questions and a cloud security assessment, which include an extensive report base on the criteria used or agreed upon.

The following sections explain each metric in a cloud security assessment and how it can correlate to the quantitative data research [4]:

- **Policy** – This will include standard policies and procedures that should be implemented. The most common is called Security Technical Implementation Guide (STIG). Which is a cybersecurity methodology for standardizing security protocols within networks, servers, computers, and logical designs to enhance overall security. These guides, when implemented, enhance security for software, hardware, physical and logical architectures to further reduce vulnerabilities.
- **Control Result** – Provides which Risk Management Framework (RMF) controls that have passed or failed in the assessment. RMF will be explained in detail later in this section.
- **Services** – Provide the list of services/systems that were evaluated and included in the assessment
- **Evaluations** – Provide the criteria that are being scored or evaluated (i.e., password complexity)
- **Security Posture** – This is a breakout of all the evaluations assessed with the amount that has failed or passed the assessment
- **Failures to Criticality** – Breaks down all the findings from a ranking to Low, Medium, and High

C. Procedure & Data Analysis Plan

In discussing the cloud security assessment as an instrument used to evaluate the quantitative data. The steps below are the procedures that would be followed to conduct the assessment, along with the deliverables that will be provided [5]:

- **Initial Document Review** of migration strategies, architecture diagrams, hardening documentation, access management policies and standards, SOPs/playbooks, and logging standards, conducted offsite in collaboration with client stakeholders
- **Onsite Workshops** to explore the cloud environment, the current security model in place, and potential security concepts and controls to implement in the future
- **Configuration Review** of the cloud platform to ensure security controls are implemented effectively, identify potential weaknesses, and confirm learnings from the onsite workshops to identify potential weaknesses that could be exploited by attackers.
- **Reporting** that details practical technical recommendations to harden the cloud environment, enhance visibility and detection and improve processes to reduce the risk of compromise.

Below are the deliverables that would be provided after the assessment:

- A snapshot of the current cloud environment, detailing existing architecture and security controls
- Security for specific cloud services aligned with the current configurations and operational processes
- Practical recommendations for enhancing visibility and detection
- Prioritized and detailed recommendations for further hardening the cloud infrastructure

There will be key focus areas that will be evaluated during each assessment as shown in Figure 2 [5]:

Governance, Risk and Compliance	Security Architecture and Networking	Identity and Access Management
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cloud governance and services • Cloud policies and standards • Threat risk assessments • Vulnerability management • Regulatory compliance requirements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cloud architecture and security controls • Network segmentation and on-premise integration • Remote system connectivity and management • Disaster recovery • Containers, configurations and security controls 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cloud authentication infrastructure, including on-premise connectivity (e.g., ADFS) • Identity management • Privilege access management • Role-based access controls
Secrets and Data Protection	DevOps	Threat Detection and Response
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data protection and loss prevention • Database security • Certificates and keys management • Encryption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pipeline configurations • System and application deployment • Secure software development life cycle • Code repository security controls 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System, database, and application logging • Security logging and centralization • Endpoint and network security controls • Cloud incident response processes

Figure 2: Core Focus Areas for Evaluation During the Assessment.

D. Risk Management Process

The Risk Management Framework (RMF) is a set of information security policies and standards the federal government developed by The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). There are three NIST special publications that cover the RMF process and cloud computing control guidance [6]:

- **NIST SP 800-37** “Guide for Applying the Risk Management Framework to Federal Information Systems”
 - Describes the formal RMF certification and accreditation process
- **NIST SP 800-53**, “Security and Privacy Controls for Federal Information Systems and Organizations”
 - Describes a structured process for integrating information security and risk management activities into system development from start to finish.
- **NIST SP 800-210**, “General Access Control Guidance for Cloud Systems”
 - Describes cloud access control characteristics and a set of general access control guidance for cloud service models

The RMF process applies a risk-based approach that considers effectiveness, efficiency, and restrictions due to regulations, directives, executive orders, and policies. The RMF process has identified the following activities, which can be applied to both new and legacy systems and are broken down into six steps [6]:

1. **Categorize** – Classify and label the information processed, stored, and shared, and the systems that are used; this is done based on an impact analysis
2. **Select** – Review the categorization and select baseline security controls; revise and add to the security control baseline as necessary, based on organization assessment of risk and local conditions
3. **Implement** – Implement the security controls and integrate with legacy systems; document how the controls are arrayed within the system and their effects on the environment
4. **Assess** – Evaluate the security controls to determine whether or not they are implemented correctly, and their quality and effectiveness

5. **Authorize** – top management tests and approves the secured system based on the accepted risk appetite to operations and assets (i.e., how much risk the organization is willing to tolerate). Management also considers the system’s operational impact on individuals and other organizations. It will identify how much risk is still present, and either authorize it or decide on changes needed.
6. **Monitor** – Set up an ongoing monitoring and assessment schedule for security controls to measure effectiveness. Document system or operation adjustments, and include impact analyses of changes made, Report findings to information security officials

As the RMF process is meant to be a continuous cycle, the evaluator can then start again from step one, all the way through to step six to account for changes in the cloud computing environment. In Figure 3, it depicts the RMF process in a continuous life cycle and the applicable SP guidelines to adhere to [6]:

Figure 3: The RMF Process.

During the RMF process, a Plan of Actions and Milestones (POA&M) is developed that describes specific measures to be taken to correct deficiencies found during the cloud security assessment. The POA&M identifies the following [7]:

- The tasks needed to correct the deficiency
- The resources required to make the plan work
- Milestones in completing the tasks
- Scheduled completion dates for the milestones
- The categorization impact level of the system

- The specific deficiencies that have been found
- What potential impact the deficiency can have on the risk exposure of the organization or the ability to perform its mission
- The proposed approach to risk mitigation
- Any rationale for accepting some risk level caused by specific deficiencies

POA&M's are key to both the authorization and the continuous monitoring process. An assessment of security controls triggers the need for a POA&M, and the POA&M deficiency item must be kept open and tracked until the deficiency has been mitigated. Continuous Monitoring uses the POA&M items as one of the criteria to select candidates for monitoring [7].

III. ANALYSIS

In any project to determine the best outcome regardless of what industry a company is in, some form of analysis has to be conducted. As mentioned in the previous section of this report, data were collected with a mix of qualitative and quantitative research. In this section, the report will review and provide the answers to the four fundamental questions in cybersecurity and also provide the results from the 2020 Amazon Web Services (AWS) cloud security assessment report.

A. Interviews

1) *What Are the Benefits?*

The first question on the survey the cybersecurity professionals answered was “What are the benefits of implementing Cloud Computing into your specific field/department? The answers to this question were all very common with the use of cloud computing in any industry today was cost-cutting. Reduced IT costs are one of the key motivators for any company to adopt cloud computing and this was a common answer among the group. The reason for this is because with cloud computing the company is utilizing the computing power and resources of a cloud service provider. This allows the company to require the employee or customer access to the application program interface (API) through an internet connection. Many companies that are not currently using a cloud computing infrastructure have to budget for system upgrades and computing resources for their employees and in some instances for the customer. Another aspect that reduces cost ties to a reduction in required IT staff. Most companies have numerous IT staff to help with maintenance and computer support, with cloud computing this can be shifted to the Cloud Service Provider (CSP). Which allows the company to have a small dedicated IT staff for the company.

The second benefit was scalability. Which is defined as the ability to increase or decrease IT resources as needed to meet changing demand. Scalability is one of the top key benefits a company would consider to move their infrastructure to the cloud. Everyone in the world has seen the benefits of this firsthand due to the Covid-19 pandemic, which resulted in 75% of the workforce having to work from home. Companies had to quickly scale up their computing resources to adapt to the surge in demand from employees working from home. Companies that had already adopted cloud computing were quickly able to see the benefits.

The third benefit was business continuity. Which is an organization's ability to ensure operations and core business functions, are not severely impacted by a disaster or unplanned incident that takes critical systems offline. This also includes company data been backed up and protected. Many large-scale companies can afford to have large data centers in various locations, in the event of a natural disaster to one data center. Smaller companies don't have the resources to do this and adopting a cloud computing environment, would allow them to back up company data and ensure it is protected in the event of a natural disaster.

The last benefit was collaboration efficiency, which enables employees to work simultaneously on documents that live "in the cloud". This allows authorized users to access files from anywhere with an internet connection. This concept has been standard practice in corporations and education, Google Drive is one of the most used collaboration tools. This program allows multiple users to update and edit documents in real-time with multiple users.

2) *Issues Affecting the Adoption of Cloud Computing*

The first issue was risk, and this can be further broken down into three parts:

1. **Policy & Organizational** – Once a company chooses a CSP they are locked into that service provider and also risk the loss of governance for the cloud infrastructure once the service is established.
2. **Legal** – This risk lies with how the CSP protects the client or companies data and who is at fault in the event of a data breach.
3. **Availability** – When you are dependent on another cloud provider, you could encounter unexpected downtime.

The next issue was security and privacy. These two topics are the main issues that companies face day-to-day even beyond just in the cloud computing environment. AWS is a very popular cloud service and has multiple safeguards in place to secure your data. The concern is how are they ensuring your data are protected? In many cases, CSPs provide a potential client a few overviews on how they protect your data but the customer doesn't have control if they feel it's more or less secure than an in-house setup. There are tiers of service a company can pay for to increase the level of protection, the increase in protection the higher the cost. The other caveat to data protection is compliance, most CSPs have internal metrics for cloud computing compliance. A few CSPs do provide FedRAMP compliance certifications but are not mandated or required by the government, unless the company is doing business with a government entity or a defense contractor. Companies also have to factor in the service level agreement that is agreed upon by both parties. CSPs provide an SLA for all customers, the risk is this agreement is very hard to customized based on the company or service required.

The last issue was data confidentiality, this is a major concern for government and commercial organizations. Since cloud service is based on being stored on various data centers all over the country or sometimes the world. The client takes the risk and has a lack of control of the physical infrastructure where the data are stored. An in-house infrastructure can provide an extra layer of physical protection from data centers. CSPs normally provide a local security company and minimum safeguards in most centers. This allows off-premises staff access to data from the CSPs customers.

3) *How Can the Issues Be Addressed and What Procedures Need to be in Place*

The last two questions were designed to be answered together to allow the questionees to provide their answer and a solution on how it can be done. The first answer was cost savings. This is something that IT departments and upper management will want to cover in great detail. In cloud computing, most services have a pay-as-you-go model. In this approach, companies can scale up or down based on the expected usage for the company. During lower peaked times a company will pay less money for the cloud services and can anticipate an increase in spending when more computing resources are needed. Before a company considers moving its network to the cloud, the IT department should build action plans to meet the organizational objectives for the company in a cloud computing environment. From a security standpoint, CSPs have the full-time job to carefully monitor security on their cloud networks as well as their clients. Companies can employ a small, dedicated staff just to monitor the companies cloud environment and this will also make it easier to meet government or company compliance requirements. The company also needs to work with the CSP to encrypt data during transit and at rest for all data stored on the cloud provider's network.

In regard to the risk, one major topic was to implement cloud and on-site backups of company data. In the event the CSPs service is disrupted or not in service, the client still has access to their data on their company networks. This will allow the company to develop contingency plans in the event of a cloud service outage. During the planning phase for cloud adoption ensure the company can choose a CSP that allows modification to the SLA. That should include the following:

- Clauses and procedures for terminating service
- Data protection techniques or services that have to be implemented
- Able to choose physical locations where data will be stored
- Procedures in place for only cleared staff can access data offsite

IV. RETURN ON INVESTMENT

Organizations are switching to the cloud at a faster rate than ever. Companies will need to incorporate a sound migration plan for any enterprise taking on cloud migration. Along with this plan, the company will want to perform due diligence to understand the costs and returns associated with the migration. Executives will want hard figures to justify the investment to themselves and management. Many organizations that choose the cloud migration path tend to use a return on investment (ROI) assessment. To determine if cloud migration will save the company money, help them achieve their organizational goals, and how long it will take them to recoup that investment [8].

A. *The Cloud ROI Formula*

The ROI formula of return over costs appears relatively simple, it can be surprisingly complicated when applied to cloud migration. Comparing on-premise vs cloud ROI calculations can be complicated and may not return enough numerical data the company would need to make decisions. As mentioned earlier in this report, cloud models range from Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Software as a Service (SaaS). In the cloud, if the service is less customized and more dependent on the cloud service provider, it will reduce the initial capital investment and increases the operational investment over time based on subscription fees.

Figure 4, summarizes the three cloud models and how they range in scope:

Figure 4: Cloud Model Service Ranges.

A particular company cloud migration can mix many of these cloud models on an application-by-application basis. Some applications may need a very custom Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) approach versus others that may only require a Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) configuration. It may be decided that there is a need to keep some applications on-premises and move others to the cloud, creating a hybrid solution.

B. Cloud Value

Cloud Value can be broken out into five categories: Agility, Productivity, Quality, Reduced Costs, and Employee Retention. Any improvements in these will have a lasting impact on any organization [8].

1) Agility

Refers to the ability to rapidly adapt and provide cost efficiency in response to changes in the business environment. Cloud computing allows companies to decrease the time it takes to provision and de-provision IT infrastructure. This speeds the delivery of IT projects that are critical to revenue growth or cost reduction, this can be calculated into a numerical value based on the IT project.

2) Productivity

The cloud provides a more productive environment for collaborative working. The flexible infrastructure that can be accessed translates into businesses enhancing their productivity among their employees and customers. Organizations can increase or scale down their operations to support their business goals such as attracting and retaining new customers or speeding up the time-to-market for the latest services.

3) Quality

The cloud can improve service and product quality through customization and enhanced user experience. The cloud provides the opportunity to automate deployments and rollbacks. The company can ship and test features faster as

many times as they want in a business day. This feature is especially important since it creates an environment for continuous improvement, improving the product and the client's experience overall.

4) Reduced Costs

Cloud computing can optimize ownership use by reducing the application total cost of ownership. This is established through reducing licensing costs, open-source adoption, and Service-Oriented Architecture (SOA) reuse adoption. The cloud also optimizes the cost associated with delivering a specified IT service capacity by aligning IT costs with IT usage, this can be effectively managed with pay-as-you-go savings. Thanks to economies of scale, cloud providers can facilitate better up-to-date resources for less money than most on-premise infrastructures.

5) Employee Retention

Cloud implementation provides the opportunity for the IT team to go through a full cultural transformation. This transformation puts cooperation, communication, and empowerment at the core of a company's values. The new culture provides the ideal scenario for team members to shift their focus from process-oriented and support tasks to research and development, and it breaks the communication barriers between many company silos. A successful movement to the cloud culture makes for happy employees that are engaged in the work they want to do, and can greatly increase employee retention.

All these categories roll up to provide any company a great deal of value. But, as mentioned, much of this value is intangible and difficult for management to translate into numeric terms. These five categories are part of the reason a company is willing to invest the move to the cloud.

C. Estimating Cost in the Cloud

Moving to the cloud means moving away from all the hardware-related, software-related, and personnel costs of managing rooms of servers and data centers towards a pay-as-you-go model with ongoing subscription fees.

Figure 5, illustrates some of the initial and ongoing costs related to a cloud transition [8]:

Figure 5: Initial and On-Going Cloud Costs.

The bulk of ongoing costs for the cloud involve subscription fees, configuration changes, and training or new hiring. To assess cloud migrations many companies, use the concept of Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) for comparing cloud solutions to their current state. TCO intends to uncover both the direct and indirect costs of owning and procuring certain assets or products. It includes a few key components:

- Acquisition/Physical Hardware Costs
- Operations Costs
- Personnel Costs

The steps for calculating TCO costs for an application are listed below:

- Audit current IT infrastructure costs
- Calculate the estimated cloud infrastructure costs
- Estimate cloud migration costs
 - Data Migration
 - Integration and Testing
 - Consulting Fees
- Approximate additional post-migration costs

Within the TCO calculations, companies often overlook and identify the hidden costs. Figure 6 identifies hidden costs as related to software development. Rows represent resource categories and columns represent IT life-cycle stages [8]:

	Acquisition	Maintenance	Upgrade/Retire
Software	Obvious Cost	Obvious Cost	Hidden Cost
Hardware	Obvious Cost	Obvious Cost	Hidden Cost
Personnel/HR	Hidden Cost	Hidden Cost	Hidden Cost
Facilities	Hidden Cost	Hidden Cost	Hidden Cost

Figure 6: Cloud Computing Hidden Cost.

D. Investing IT Resources in the Cloud

To truly understand the ROI for cloud adoption, we have to understand how value is created from investing in IT. Figure 7, shows a comparison of demand for traditional IT resources versus cloud-based resources [4]:

Figure 7: Traditional IT Resources vs. Cloud-Based.

Traditional on-premise infrastructure requires provisioning resources for the companies estimated demand. In most cases, this translates into underutilized resources and large capital expenditures (represented as the blue stair-stepping line graph above). Cloud services (represented by the yellow line) grow as an on-demand model that provides the necessary resources at the right time, aligning with the companies demand and minimizing downtime. It is important to note that the ROI of cloud services is directly related to how cloud-native those services are. The deeper the infusion into cloud services, the bigger the return. In traditional systems, incorporating new technology, adding a new product, or implementing a new feature is often a lengthy process.

Figure 8, illustrates how the timeline for these kinds of deployments can be greatly reduced in the cloud:

Figure 8: Cloud Deployment Time Comparison.

With a cloud infrastructure, it can allow quick access to a broad set of resources. The company can set up fast installation and configuration of their software, do all the necessary testing, take the new product or feature to market, or in the worst-case scenario. Fail fast and only pay for the time utilized for those resources. The increased speed provides the perfect scenario for developing new sources of revenue at a faster rate and potential innovation from quick access to experimentation. Cloud computing allows companies to focus their attention on doing things that help grow revenue, increase customer engagement, and open new product channels. That is the true compound return on investment of cloud computing technology [8].

V. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The final section of this report with a combination of the data gathered and analysis conducted. Provides a company's cloud security architect recommendations to help prevent some of the issues addressed in this report.

A. DevSecOps Adoption for Cloud Security

DevSecOps is defined as integrating security practices within the development process that involves creating a 'Security as Code' culture with ongoing flexible collaboration between release engineers and security teams. This allows breaking the norm of having security as a separate process. DevSecOps allows for security integration across all stages of software development while addressing security concerns during the System Development Life Cycle (SDLC) and not just at the end. The DevSecOps approach for cloud security requires some detailed planning and a cultural change with the company's IT department. The planning stages require security teams to [9]:

- Collaborate with development teams as they move code to the cloud and close monitoring of quality in the production cycle.
- Work with the quality analysis and development teams in deciding qualifier and parameter aspects required for code approval

There is a six-step continuous process to successfully implement DevSecOps into the cloud is shown in Figure 9 [9]:

Figure 9: Veritis Six-Step DevSecOps Implementation Process.

- **Code Analysis** – During a software’s lifecycle, continuous improvements to the code will be required. Agile development teams utilize this in today’s environments, but traditional security models are unable to meet the rapid delivery cycles. Agile methodologies help companies deliver updates at a faster rate while also conducting code analysis as part of quality assurance.
- **Automated Testing** - Automation is one of the key principles DevSecOps automated testing simplifies the testing process with a minimum set of tools and scripts. Since this is automated, it can perform the same task every time and completely avoid human error. Doing this at every stage of the process chain saves time and gives a final quality output.
- **Change Management** – Collaboration with the developers in key processes like security makes an effective change management process. Making them aware of related tools and providing expertise in addressing critical issues ensures timely remediation and attention to potential threats and vulnerabilities.
- **Compliance Monitoring** - Compliance continues to be major for any company especially when it comes to cloud adoption. Having the required regulations established is equally important during new code creation or modifying the existing code. Providing evidence and sharing the results with the team keep you prepared for audits and reports. Ensuring the team has the right compliance process in place reduces the stress at the time of formal audit and keeping up the transparency for the company.

- **Threat Investigation** – Ensuring the company has regular monitoring of cloud security, minus the tools and procedures in place. Continuous discovery, threat investigation, regular security scans, and code reviews are key to the identification of any possible vulnerabilities.
- **Personnel Training** – Training personnel internally is also important for any company. This can be provided by introducing certification courses and hands-on training on specific topics or interests. When the team is more knowledgeable this will inadvertently allow the company to be more successful.

B. FedRAMP Compliance

The US government adopted a “cloud-first” initiative to ease agency data frustrations and compliance it established the Federal Risk and Authorization Management Program (FedRAMP). Many companies assume that FedRAMP applies only to those companies seeking to work with federal agencies, FedRAMP compliance can benefit the private sector as well. Cloud computing services are utilized for managing, analyzing, and storing data and these services remain a primary target for malicious hackers. Ensuring your CSP is FedRAMP compliant can ensure the likely hood of not being vulnerable to a malicious attacker on the companies cloud network. There are three key problems FedRAMP solves [10]:

- Focuses specifically on security elements unique to CSPs
- Security controls go beyond the NIST baseline requirements
- Requires a third-party assessment organization to certify the security controls

Companies that apply the FedRAMP framework to their evaluation of cloud services and products can achieve the following benefits:

- Significant cost and time savings compared to carrying out independent assessments, many of which can often be redundant
- Uniform evaluation and authorization of cloud information security controls
- Enhanced insights into cloud security controls
- Confidence in the validity of assessments and the reduction of cloud security concerns
- A faster cloud adoption roadmap

In Figure 10, is the approval and authorization process for an organization to become FedRAMP complaint [10]:

Figure 10: FedRAMP Authorization Process.

C. Customized Service Level Agreements

When a company considers moving to the cloud the foundation of the agreement between the CSP and the client is the Service Level Agreement (SLA). An SLA outlines what the provider and customer are responsible for in regard to using the service. The contract allows the company to know upfront what specifically the cloud provider implements and manages. It also gives the client knowledge of what they will contribute to continue using the service [11]. It is recommended to include the following before signing an SLA with a CSP:

- **Availability** – The SLA should cover and include the CSPs promised availability and some might break down this depending on a specific time frame (i.e., 99.9% during business hours). The terms should also include the policy and procedures for unexpected downtime, which includes alerting users while providing status updates on service repairs and maintenance.
- **Data Ownership** – The SLA should specifically outline its data ownership policies so that everything is transparent and clear, and this should also include that all ownership rights of data belong to the client.
- **Cloud Hardware and Software** – The CSP should outline the hardware that the cloud services rely on including servers, data centers, and other applicable devices. Depending on the organization, include geographical limitations of where the company's data can be stored (i.e., only on US servers)

- **Disaster Recovery and Backup** – In the event of a disaster, the CSP should have plans and procedures in place to prevent the loss of the client’s data. The SLA should have a section that describes the disaster recovery and backup solutions in detail. Depending on the client the SLA can also include the CSP to provide automatic backups and snapshots of the company’s data.
- **Customer Responsibilities** – Ensure the SLA outlines responsibilities that both the CSP and client agree on. The SLA has to include what the company and the CSP are liable for in regard to data loss or cyber-related incidents.

D. Implement a Small In-House Cloud Department

It is recommended for any company moving to a cloud infrastructure to assign individuals or a small department with the sole responsibility of the companies cloud management. This would include the following duties and more:

- Responsible for cloud budgets and forecast reporting to management
- Responsible for working directly with the CSP for issues, maintenance, or service
- Responsible for continued FedRAMP compliance and audits
- Responsible for 24/7 security monitoring of the companies cloud networks

E. Conclusion

In conclusion, this report has discussed the challenges cybersecurity architects face in a cloud computing environment. It provided qualitative and quantitative data that consisted of one-on-one interviews and a comprehensive survey among 427 cybersecurity professionals. It also included the unique take on ROI and the recommendations to some of the challenges faced. Although this report didn’t cover every challenge in the cloud computing realm, it does address some of the major ones that are affecting cloud computing infrastructures around the world.

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